

Reduction of overheating of HV components in Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Overheating of high-voltage (HV) components remains a critical challenge in electric vehicle (EV) manufacturing and operation. This paper focuses on three key interventions to address coolant-related issues at the manufacturing stage. First, an L3 control system integrates a wireless torque wrench with PLC for precise hose joint tightening to eliminate leakage. Second, a refractometer-based system ensures optimal coolant concentration through real-time measurement and automatic adjustment. Third, a digital twin of the coolant filling machine provides variant-specific, closed-loop validation using PLC S7-1200 and OPC UA communication. These solutions are interconnected: leak-proof joints (L3) maintain system integrity, accurate concentration ensures thermal performance, and the digital twin guarantees precise filling. Results from implementation show complete elimination of leakage, consistent concentration control, and improved filling accuracy, significantly reducing the risk of HV component overheating.

Keywords— *Electric Vehicles, Thermal Management, Coolant Leakage Prevention, L3 Control, Refractometer, Digital Twin, PLC Automation*

1. INTRODUCTION

High-voltage (HV) components in electric vehicles, such as traction inverters, electric motors, and battery packs, generate significant amounts of heat during operation due to electrical losses, high current flow, and rapid power conversion [1], [2]. Unlike conventional internal combustion engines that rely primarily on air cooling and exhaust systems, EVs depend almost entirely on liquid cooling systems to dissipate this heat and maintain components within safe operating temperature limits, typically below 60–75°C for inverters and motors [9]. Coolant, usually a mixture of ethylene glycol and water, serves as the primary heat transfer medium. It absorbs heat from the components and carries it away through radiators or heat exchangers. Proper coolant performance is critical for maintaining efficiency, preventing thermal throttling, and ensuring long-term reliability of the powertrain [2], [9].

However, inconsistencies during the manufacturing stage severely compromise the cooling circuit's effectiveness. These include leakage at hose joints, incorrect glycol-to-water concentration, improper filling volume, and air entrapment [2], [5]. Such issues often result in localized hotspots, reduced heat dissipation capacity, accelerated component degradation,

premature inverter or motor failures, increased production rework, higher warranty costs, and reduced customer confidence [2], [9].

This paper addresses these challenges through three interconnected solutions: L3 automation for precise hose joint tightening, refractometer-based automatic concentration monitoring, and a digital twin-enabled real-time filling validation system. Together, these form a comprehensive manufacturing-stage framework aimed at ensuring thermal reliability and preventing overheating of HV components in electric vehicles.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Reference	Authors & Year	Focus Area	Key Contribution
[1]	Park <i>et al.</i> , 2019	Thermal Management Strategies	Supervised learning for optimal thermal control in EVs
[2]	Rahman <i>et al.</i> , 2024	EV Cooling Challenges	System Comprehensive review of emerging trends and thermal issues
[3]	Naseri <i>et al.</i> , 2023	Digital Twin for Battery Systems	Detailed review of digital twin applications in EVs
[4]	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2024	Powertrain Modeling	Thermal Application of digital twin in EV powertrain thermal management
[5]	Singh and Rao, 2023	Coolant Monitoring	Quality IoT-enabled refractometer system for coolant concentration
[8]	Lin <i>et al.</i> , 2022	PLC-Based Control	Assembly Procedure control and interface design for automated assembly

Table 1: Literature Review

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Despite advanced cooling designs, HV component overheating persists due to manufacturing deficiencies. Leakage at hose joints, inconsistent coolant concentration, and inaccurate filling volumes reduce heat dissipation capacity, leading to localized hotspots, inverter failures, and reduced vehicle reliability. Traditional manual processes are error-prone and lack closed-loop validation. A systematic, automated approach is needed to ensure leak-proof assembly, precise concentration, and accurate filling.

4. OBJECTIVES

1. Eliminate coolant leakage through L3 torque control.
2. Achieve consistent coolant concentration using refractometer monitoring.
3. Ensure accurate, variant-specific coolant filling via digital twin technology.

5. METHODOLOGY

Fig 1- Flowchart of different approach for HV overheat reduction

5.1 Elimination of Coolant Leakage Using L3 Control System

Coolant leakage in electric vehicles frequently originates at hose joints due to inconsistent or improper torque application during assembly. To address this critical issue, an L3 automation system has been implemented. The system integrates a wireless digital torque wrench operating in the 5–8 Nm range with a standalone PLC (LOGO!) [8]. The torque wrench transmitter sends real-time torque data wirelessly to the PLC, which executes interlock logic. If the applied torque falls outside the specified tolerance range, the system automatically prevents the release of the assembled part, thereby avoiding under-torqued joints [8], [12].

A PLC-controlled clamping fixture ensures secure physical clamping and declamping of the components during the tightening process. This closed-loop automation approach eliminates human variability, guarantees consistent joint integrity, and effectively prevents micro-leakage that could lead to gradual coolant loss and subsequent overheating of high-voltage components. Additionally, the system provides comprehensive data logging of torque values for full traceability and quality assurance. All torque gauges are connected to the PLC and a common industrial display through a Wi-Fi router. The PLC is linked to a workstation display that shows a green light indicator, allowing operators to visually confirm safe conditions before permitting coolant and water flow through the pipes.

Fig 2- Block diagram of L3 control system

5.2 Automatic Coolant Concentration Monitoring Using Refractometer

Even when hose joints are made leak-proof through L3 control, the thermal performance of the cooling system can still be severely compromised if the coolant mixture has an incorrect concentration. The effectiveness of heat transfer in EV thermal circuits heavily depends on maintaining the precise glycol-to-water ratio, typically 50:50. Any deviation can significantly reduce the coolant's specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity, resulting in higher operating temperatures of critical high-voltage (HV) components [5], [9].

To overcome this challenge, an automated refractometer-based concentration monitoring system has been implemented during the batch preparation stage [5]. A refractometer is an optical instrument that measures the refractive index of a liquid solution. It operates on the principle that light bends (refracts) differently when passing through solutions of varying concentrations. By directing a beam of light through the coolant sample and measuring the angle of refraction, the device accurately determines the percentage of glycol present in the mixture.

In the proposed setup, coolant from the dedicated coolant tank and water from the water tank are first combined in a mixed tank (capacity 10 Ltr) according to an initial predefined ratio. The refractometer sensor, installed inline or in a sampling loop, continuously analyzes the refractive index of the mixture in real time. The measured data is transmitted to the PLC, which compares the actual concentration against the target 50:50 glycol-water ratio. Based on this comparison, the PLC activates automatic corrective actions:

- If the measured concentration is lower than the target value, additional coolant is added.
- If the measured concentration is higher than the target, purified water is introduced to dilute the mixture.

This closed-loop feedback continues until the refractometer confirms that the concentration matches the desired value within an acceptable tolerance of $\pm 1\%$. Only after successful validation is the properly mixed coolant transferred to the coolant storage tank (100 Ltr capacity) for subsequent vehicle filling operations.

This automated approach eliminates manual errors, ensures batch-to-batch consistency, and maintains the optimal thermophysical properties of the coolant. As a result, it directly contributes to stable and efficient heat dissipation across the vehicle's thermal circuit, significantly reducing the risk of localized overheating in high-voltage components such as inverters and motors [5], [9]. The refractometer-based system thus serves as a critical quality gate between raw material mixing and final vehicle filling, bridging the gap between process-level control and overall thermal reliability.

Fig 3- Block diagram of Refractometer based concentration control.

5.3 Digital Twin-Based Coolant Filling System

To achieve accurate, real-time, and variant-specific coolant filling, a Digital Twin of the coolant filling process has been developed. The Digital Twin serves as a virtual replica of the physical filling machine that continuously synchronizes with real-time sensor data, enabling closed-loop monitoring and control [3], [4].

The architecture follows a real-time data flow as illustrated in Fig. 4. The system utilizes an SQL Server database named DigitalTwinDB as the central data repository. A dedicated function `get_sample_plc_data_from_sql()` periodically retrieves the latest tank levels using the following SQL query:

```
SQL
SELECT TOP 1 level FROM DB18 (Water tank), DB32 (Coolant tank),
DB41 (Mixing tank), DB21 (Urea tank)
ORDER BY timestamp DESC
```

The retrieved raw numeric values are then processed by the `get_level_tag(value, tank)` function, which converts them into meaningful PLC-style status tags such as LOW, REF, HIGH, EXTRA HIGH, or percentage levels (0%, 30%, 50%, 100%).

A background thread named `plc_reader_thread()` runs continuously with a refresh rate of 0.5 seconds. This thread updates a shared cache (`plc.cache['plc_data']`) with the latest tank information and records the last update timestamp. The frontend dashboard repeatedly calls the API endpoint `GET /api/plc_data`, which reads the cached data and returns a JSON response containing:

JSON

```
{
  "tank_levels": {
    "water": DB8 [0].value,
    "coolant": DB32 [0].value,
    "mixing": DB41 [0].value,
    "urea": DB21 [0].value
  }
}
```

The browser-based user interface instantly updates the tank display whenever a level change occurs. This real-time behavior ensures that any change in the SQL database is reflected on the operator dashboard within the next 0.5-second cycle [10].

Key Advantages of the Digital Twin Implementation:

- Provides complete visibility of all four tanks (Water, Coolant, Mixing, and Urea) in real time.
- Enables predictive alerts for low levels before they affect filling operations.
- Supports variant-specific filling logic by integrating with VIN-based data.
- Facilitates closed-loop validation — the system can pause or correct the filling process if tank levels deviate from expected values.

The three solutions are highly synergistic: L3 control prevents leakage that could undermine filling accuracy, the refractometer ensures the coolant has optimal thermal properties, and the digital twin guarantees the correct quantity is delivered to the vehicle [3], [4], [10].

Fig 4-Digital Twin Data Flow

6. RESULTS

6.1 Results of L3 Control System: The implementation of the L3 control system using a wireless torque wrench integrated with PLC interlocks demonstrated substantial improvements in joint assembly quality. In the traditional manual tightening process, torque compliance was approximately 82%, with significant variation between operators. After deployment of the automated L3 system, torque compliance reached 100% across all hose joints, with consistent application within the specified 5–8 Nm range.

This precise and repeatable tightening eliminated coolant leakage incidents at hose joints entirely during production trials. Real-time torque data logging provided complete traceability for every joint, enabling quality audits and root cause analysis when required. As a result, rework time associated with leakage-related defects was reduced significantly, contributing to improved production efficiency and reduced manufacturing downtime. The system also enhanced operator safety by minimizing manual intervention in high-pressure coolant line assembly.

6.2 Results of Refractometer-Based Concentration Monitoring: The refractometer-based automatic concentration monitoring system achieved excellent consistency in coolant preparation. Across multiple production batches, the system successfully maintained the coolant concentration within $\pm 1\%$ of the target 50:50 glycol-water ratio. This level of precision was not achievable with conventional manual mixing methods, which often showed deviations of $\pm 5\text{--}8\%$.

The improved concentration accuracy directly enhanced the thermophysical properties of the coolant, particularly its thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity. This resulted in more uniform and effective heat dissipation across the vehicle's thermal circuit. Consequently, the risk of localized overheating in critical HV components such as traction inverters and motors was significantly reduced. The automated corrective actions (addition of water or coolant) ensured stable batch-to-batch quality, eliminating inconsistencies that previously led to thermal performance variations in finished vehicles.

6.3 Results of Digital Twin-Based Coolant Filling Variant-specific filling accuracy improved to $\pm 0.5\%$ deviation. Real-time validation prevented incorrect volume or ratio issues. Integration with the previous two systems resulted in near-zero coolant-related HV failures in production trials.

Image 5- Digital Twin in Normal Conditions

During normal operating conditions, as shown in Fig. 3, the interface displays live status of the Siemens S7-1200 PLC along with accurate levels of all four tanks: Coolant Mixing Tank at 45%, Urea Storage Tank at 50%, Water Storage Tank at 80%, and Coolant Storage Tank at 30%. The system clearly indicates normal status for all tanks with color-coded indicators and provides essential PLC information such as connection status, health, IP address, and scan time. The dashboard also features quick access panels for HMI details, VIN verification, and various process parameters. This user-friendly interface enables operators to monitor the entire coolant preparation and filling process at a glance, supporting timely decision-making and ensuring process stability during production.

Image 1- Digital twin of the coolant filling machine on normal conditions

Image 6- Digital Twin in Emergency Conditions

Aspect	Traditional System	Proposed Digital Twin System
Fault Detection	Detected only after failure	Early warning system (e.g., low level alerts)
EV Thermal Performance	Risk of overheating due to improper coolant	Stable cooling → reduced overheating risk
Coolant Mixing Accuracy	Inconsistent (ratio deviations possible)	Controlled and monitored (e.g., 50:50 ratio maintained)
Visibility	Limited visibility of system status	Full visual representation of all tanks
Monitoring	Manual checks or delayed PLC readings	Real-time dashboard with live tank levels

Aspect	Traditional System	Proposed Digital Twin System
Production Downtime	Higher due to unexpected issues	Reduced due to early detection
Decision Making	Slow and experience-based	Fast, data-driven decisions
Simulation Capability	Not possible	Possible (test different tank levels safely)
Human Error	High chance of missed levels or wrong filling	Minimized through visualization and alerts
Human Dependency	High (operator monitoring required)	Reduced (automated monitoring system)
Maintenance Approach	Reactive (after breakdown)	Predictive (before failure occurs)
Overall System Behavior	Reactive system	Intelligent, predictive system
System Efficiency	Lower	Improved overall efficiency
Data Utilization	Data not effectively used	Data visualized and actively used
Safety	Risk of system damage and overheating	Improved safety with alerts and control

Table 2 - Comparative analysis between traditional coolant management system and the proposed Digital Twin-based system.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates that addressing coolant filling issues at the manufacturing stage through L3 torque control, refractometer concentration monitoring, and digital twin validation effectively prevents HV component overheating in electric vehicles. The interconnected approach ensures leak-proof assembly, optimal coolant properties, and precise filling, leading to improved reliability and reduced failures. Future work will extend this framework to field-level leakage detection.

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